

The Annamalai Iota Function: Novel Special Function

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Abstract: This paper introduces a novel special function, called the Annamalai iota function $\iota(s)$, in the area of analytic number theory. The sum of the Dirichlet eta function and the Annamalai iota function is equal to zero.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the eta function and the zeta function [17-19]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science, and medicine [20].

2. Harmonic Series, Dirichlet Eta Function, and Riemann Zeta Function

The harmonic series is defined by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots$$

and the alternative harmonic series is shown below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}$$

The Riemann zeta function for all complex numbers is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots$$

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\Re(s) > 1$.

The Dirichlet eta function relating to the alternative harmonic series is defined by

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The Dirichlet eta function $\eta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\Re(s) > 0$.

3. Annamalai Iota Function

The author of this article introduces the Annamalai iota function as follows:

The Annamalai iota function $l(s)$ for all complex numbers is defined by

$$l(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s},$$

The Annamalai iota function $l(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $Re(s) > 0$.

Note that $l(1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n}$.

Theorem 3.1: $l(s) + \eta(s) = 0$.

Proof. Case (i): Let us prove this theorem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} l(s) + \eta(s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} \\ l(s) + \eta(s) &= \left(-1 + \frac{1}{2^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} - \frac{1}{5^s} + \dots\right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \dots\right) \\ \therefore l(s) + \eta(s) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2: $\frac{1}{2}(2\zeta(s) + l(s) + \eta(s)) = \zeta(s)$.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(s) + \eta(s) &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \dots\right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \dots\right) \\ \zeta(s) + \eta(s) &= 2 + \frac{2}{3^s} + \frac{2}{5^s} + \frac{2}{7^s} + \frac{2}{9^s} + \dots = 2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \dots\right) \\ \frac{1}{2}(\zeta(s) + \eta(s)) &= 1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \dots \\ \frac{1}{2}(\zeta(s) + l(s)) &= \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

From the above equations, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}(\zeta(s) + \eta(s)) + \frac{1}{2}(\zeta(s) + l(s)) &= 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots \\ \frac{1}{2}(\zeta(s) + \eta(s) + \zeta(s) + l(s)) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}. \\ \frac{1}{2}(2\zeta(s) + l(s) + \eta(s)) &= \zeta(s). \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved.

Case (ii): This theorem is proved using the theorem 3.1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}(2\zeta(s) + l(s) + \eta(s)) &= \frac{1}{2}(2\zeta(s) + 0), \quad (\because l(s) + \eta(s) = 0). \\ \frac{1}{2}(2\zeta(s) + l(s) + \eta(s)) &= \zeta(s). \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved.

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has introduced the Annamalai iota function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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